

Academics experiences on students support in an open Distance and e-learning university in South Africa

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Abstract

Student support has always been linked to success and retention in higher institutions of learning. Moreover, within Open Distance and e-Learning (ODEL) institutions of higher learning, educational access and opportunities are provided for a broader student population that would otherwise be excluded from accessing education. This qualitative study explored the academics' experiences in providing student support within an Open Distance and e-Learning institution of higher learning in South Africa using a case study research design. Purposive sampling included ten academics from the College of Education. Data were collected by means of a self-developed qualitative open-ended questionnaire and literature control. Thematic content analysis was used to find emerging themes. Five themes relating to academics' experiences on student support, namely, academics conceptualised student support, Strategies used to facilitate student support, enabling factors in promoting student support, Challenges in providing student support and best decisions made by academics to provide student support emerged from the study. The study contributes to existing knowledge on student support by highlighting the experiences of academics in an open distance learning. The study recommends (i) collaborated, and integrated student support; (ii) continuous and professional development regarding emotional and psychological well-being; (iii) ICT support for all students including those in remote areas; and (iv) language and academic skills training.

Key words: *Academics experiences, student support, open distance and e-learning university.*

1. Introduction

Student support has always been linked to success and retention in higher institutions of learning. Moreover, within Open Distance and e-Learning (ODEL) institutions of higher learning, educational access and opportunities are provided for a broader student population that would otherwise be excluded from accessing education (Moore & Kearsley 2012; Shale 2010). As such, ODeL the student population is diverse in terms of background, geographies, preparedness, age, and maturity (Swartz et al. 2017). Hence, Shikulo and Lekheto (2020) argue that robust support is necessary for students to succeed in higher education.

Ideally, openness in these institutions should translate to the removal of barriers such as time, place and situation that would prevent access (Kanuka & Brooks 2010). In addition, they should reflect principles of lifelong learning, learner centredness, flexibility in the provision of learning, removing barriers to learning, recognition of prior learning, provision of student support and construction of learning and assist students to cope independently (White Paper for Post-School Education and Training 2013; Letseka 2016; Nsamba & Makoe 2017).

While enabling factors are created for students to access ODeL institutions, students must adapt to various processes such as time management, handling the course content without being tutored on a face-to-face basis, understanding processes for online submission of assignments and examinations, and juggling their personal responsibilities as individuals. For these reasons, scholars such as Keller-Schneider (2014), Dweck et al (2014), Proctor et al (2012), contend that students in such institutions should be independent, regulate their learning as a basic requirement of the learning process, demonstrate a strong sense of discipline and should be motivated to learn. Additionally, as an author, I think students should demonstrate competencies in using information and communications technology (ICT) for accessing coursework, assignments, participating in students' forums and using other social media for learning. Furthermore, students should learn and use academic writing skills, manage volumes of content knowledge as well as apply these in real-life experiences.

However, incidences of high drop-out rates, academic dishonesty and prolonged completion of qualifications have been observed as a major problem in such institutions. These observations suggest ineffective academic support and a lack of collaborated and integrated student support services. Thus, the process of student support is often fragmented as it takes different modes. Moreover, academics seem to focus on the students meeting academic outcomes while neglecting the student support services and academic development and support that focus on the psychological needs, career paths, study skills and other aspects affecting students.

The success of students in ODeL settings depends on how students are supported holistically to meet their academic outcomes, yet little is known about the experiences of academics and how these experiences influence student support processes and practices.

1.2. Student support in ODeL

There are different views to describe student support. As such, Lumadi (2021) writes that the concept of student support is used to include different services with the aim of assisting students to achieve their learning outcomes, gain knowledge and successfully complete their studies. Also, researchers often use the concepts *academic advising* and

guidance which include working with students to construct knowledge work with them to enable them to construct knowledge (Schreiber et al. 2018; De Klerk et al. 2017). On the other hand, the concept student Shabani and Maboe (2021) uses the concept student services and they indicate that such services also aim at addressing the needs and barriers students encounter to ensure that they succeed academically. Pitsoane and Matjila (2021) cite counselling services which basically assist students in career decisions relating to their interests, abilities, and personalities; and academic services that include tutoring and the facilitation of academic development and support to refer to what constitute student support. Therefore, these services are aimed at ensuring that students are supported to meet their academic outcomes. As a result, Berger et al. (2019) suggest collaborative partnership to support complex and diverse student needs.

Prinsloo (2010) identifies three categories of student support namely: academic (cognitive) support; affective support (also includes social elements); and administrative (non-academic) support, including technical support. Academic support includes content-related and non-content related student support. Its purpose is to enhance the cognitive dimension of the learning experience. Therefore, academic support is integrated into the course design of the learning materials and resources (Prinsloo 2010). Affective support relates to students' lifeworlds and impacts the student's success and retention. Affective student support often requires specialised interventions by trained staff even though these can be offered by other stakeholders. Such support provides pastoral care and guidance to students and is based on three distinct phases – prior to registration, after registration and post-graduation (UNISA 2010). Therefore, affective support encompasses a holistic consideration of the student as an individual. On the other hand, non-academic support includes factors that are outside the loci of control of students and depends on the effectiveness and efficiency of institutional systems, procedures, and processes (Prinsloo 2010).

1.3. Roles of academics in providing student support

The core responsibilities of academics are teaching and learning. However, academics are also responsible for conducting research, academic citizenship, and community-engaged scholarship. As a core function, academics are expected to ensure that students are successful in meeting the desired outcomes. Academic staff are therefore at the centre of providing student support and have a responsibility to do so. Hence, they need to demonstrate certain key attributes. I view these attributes to include examples such as positioning themselves as an invitational education practitioner; being student centred; taking a solution-focused stance; keeping up with the 21st-century skills for teaching and continuous professional development; and keeping a balance between a proactive and reactive approach, as strategies for maximising student support.

Positioning oneself as an invitational practitioner could be demonstrated by communicating caring when giving feedback or addressing student queries. Academics can also demonstrate invitational qualities of respect, trust, optimism, and intentionally as expounded by Purkey (1996). Respect requires believing that people (students) are able, valuable, and responsible and should be treated accordingly. Trust could be reflected by education that encourages cooperative and collaborative learning. In terms of optimism, academics should understand that students have their own untapped potential and should be valued as human beings.

Baeten et al (2013) assert that student-centredness relates to viewing knowledge through lenses of social and relational processes and therefore prioritises students' individual processes of constructing personal knowledge and understanding, rather than the rote mastery of course content. Student-centredness also allows flexibility, self-reflection and change that should be displayed by both academics and their students. Academics who value student-centredness place learning at the centre of the classroom environment and create conducive learning for students, where both teacher and students share responsibility for creating a meaningful learning experience (McCabe & O'Connor 2014). Student-centredness also means that they provide supportive relationships in the classroom and create a space that feels safe and trustworthy to student learners. Wright (2011) suggests that a student-centred instructor favours democratic and collaborative approaches to teaching that empower students to be active participants in their learning. For Baeten et al (2013), learner-centred instructors provide opportunities for their students to explore topics of interest in depth by adhering less strictly to course content.

Keeping a balance between proactive and reactive factors requires academics to plan and to anticipate problem areas – such as prior to examinations and with the submission of assignments. Academics should also engage students via multimedia during the process of learning. It is also important that academics use technology as part of their teaching methodology to assess and to connect with students. In this way, accessibility will be enhanced, and distance will be reduced (Castro Sánchez and Aleman 2011). Accessibility also relates to information and technology communication (ICT) equipment. Examples include computers, the internet and online libraries. These resources enhance learning as students can complete their assignments and projects and academics can also use ICTs to provide online support. Such competencies require continuous professional development for academics so that they can use them to maximise student support. It is for these reasons that this article explored and academics' experiences of providing academic support within an ODeL context.

2. Research methods and design

A qualitative approach was deemed appropriate in this study, which explored the experiences of academics regarding student support at an ODeL university. The aim of qualitative research is to explore and understand the meaning an individual or group ascribes to a social or human problem (Creswell 2009; Ivankova & Wingo 2018). A qualitative approach was used to explore and understand academic experiences concerning student support within an ODeL context, which as Merriam and Grenier (2019) indicate, is their social context. Also, the approach helped to uncover the meaning academics attach to providing student support in their natural setting (Merriam 2009; Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Creswell 2018; McMillan & Schumacher 2014). Furthermore, it was used because of its strength of being flexible in nature (McMillan & Schumacher 2010; Maxwell 2012), allowing me as the researcher to be open-minded and curious as to what academics' experience regarding student support. Hence, I could capture multiple perspectives and shared realities (Creswell 2015) as experienced by participants.

A case study research design was used described by Nieuwenhuis (2016) and Yin (2018) as an empirical inquiry that investigates a contemporary phenomenon in its real-life context when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not clear

and in which multiple sources of evidence are used. The case study research design allowed me to collect detailed information on student support using a variety of data-collection procedures over a sustained period (Creswell 2009, Maxwell, 2012).

3. Study population and sampling strategy

The population of the study included lecturers from the College of Education (CEDU) at the University of South Africa (UNISA). The CEDU comprises ten departments. Participants were selected by using purposive non-probability sampling (Flick, 2018) which included information-rich cases to understand something about those cases without needing or desiring to generalise the findings to the population (McMillan & Schumacher 2010; 2014). Participants were selected as they were considered people who would provide rich descriptions of their experiences (Babbie 2013; Creswell & Creswell 2018; Flick 2018) regarding providing student support in an ODeL context. Their experiences would thus enrich the researcher's understanding of the study being explored. The selection criteria were that the participants must be lecturers responsible for a module or modules in CEDU. Participation in the study was voluntary.

TABLE 1: Characteristics of participants (n = 10)

Participants	Gender	Position	ODL experience
P1	female	Senior Lecture	6 yrs.
P2	female	Senior Lecturer	11 yrs
P3	female	Senior lecturer	12 yrs.
P4	female	Senior Lecturer	8yrs
P5	male	Senior lecturer	17 yrs.
P6	male	Professor	10y yrs.
P7	female	Senior lecturer	8 yrs.
P8	male	Senior Lecturer	5 yrs.
P9	male	Senior lecturer	10yrs
P10	female	Senior lecturer	9 yrs.

4. Data Collection

A self-developed qualitative questionnaire was used as the main instrument to collect data. Questionnaires were considered as useful tools to collect original data about people, their behaviour, experiences and social interactions, attitudes and opinions, as well as awareness of events (McLafferty 2010). Open-ended questions were designed in a manner that they could be analysed qualitatively. According to Beckett and Clegg (2007), open-ended questions give participants a voice, thus allowing them to question the concepts and structure of the questionnaire. In essence, using open-ended questions allowed for alternative interpretations and for adding explanations and justifications for the answers Popping (2015). Furthermore, open-ended questionnaires can be analysed qualitatively and that they can include discussions and critical analysis. Also, open-ended questions were used because they prevented bias during data collection and allowed enough time for the participants to answer the questions. To enhance data

collection, literature control was also used to support or refute the findings (Bowen 2009).

5. Data analyses

Data were analysed using thematic analysis (Nowell et al. 2017). The process involved presenting quotations from the open-ended questionnaire using the participants' actual words. These were then coded and arranged in a logical manner around themes (Cohen et al. 2011; Creswell & Creswell 2018). The findings were also corroborated with literature control.

6. Results

The themes that emerged from the study were categorised under the following: academics' descriptions of student support and its importance in an ODeL context; strategies used to facilitate student support; enabling factors in promoting student support; challenges in providing support and best decisions made to maximise student support.

Theme 1: Academics' conceptualization of student support and its importance in an ODeL context

It emerged that academics conceptualised student support as providing cognitive, emotional, and social assistance; addressing barriers that may hinder learning; motivating students to succeed in their studies; recognising students' skills, talents, abilities, and experiences; and communicating with students concerning all aspects.

To express their views, academics indicated:

“Student support involves identifying students at risk, offering interventions, and providing cognitive, emotional, and social support.” – P6.

“It constitutes responding to their [students] concerns and problems, and entails communicating with students in all aspects to give them support to understand their work, enabling them to succeed in their studies.” – P9.

“It means that you are considering all aspects that may affect students like social aspects, emotional and so on” – P7.

“For me it means helping students and making sure that they think and apply themselves when doing their work and also teaching them those cognitive skills.” – P5.

The descriptions highlight that academic view students holistically. These aspects are essential in learning. The findings affirm Simpson's (2015) view who points out that cognitive and emotional support is important for developing the students' learning. For Secreto and Pamulaklakin (2015), the purpose of student support is to respond to the cognitive, psychological, emotional, and social needs of students. On the other hand, Cao et al. (2020) and Yildirim and Tanriverdi, (2020) also affirm that social support plays a critical role in an individual's mental resilience.

Regarding addressing students' barriers as a way of providing student support, they mentioned:

- *"I consider students' social environment, e.g., loneliness of distance learning, and assist to connect a particular student with his/her peers. In that way, removing barriers such as loneliness means that you are supporting [the] students."* – P2
- *"Provision of student support is sometimes also through accepting 'walk-in' appointments even if the student did not set up an appointment. In that way, the student does not have to go back without information. Sometimes, I just make a proper appointment with the student if the student found me busy."* – P5
- *"it means removing obstacles that prevent a student to do well in their modules."* – P4
- *"I view removing barriers such as language as part of student support. I have seen students improving their academic performance when the language barrier has been attended to."* – P8

The expressions above highlight academics' acknowledgement that barriers to learning are multifaceted. Evidently, academics are perceptive, flexible, and accommodative in addressing such barriers. As a Result, Rotar (2020) and Muljana & Placencia (2018) also point out that overcoming barriers to learning by ensuring learner engagement and motivation is essential for success in online higher education.

On the other hand, motivating students was expressed as:

- *"Student support involves motivating students by giving constructive feedback in written assignments."* – P10.
- *"It constitutes responding to their concerns and problems. I think in doing so, students are influenced to be more motivated to learn and to attain academic outcomes."* – P5.
- *"If they want to quit, you encourage them [not to quit]. It also means explaining why they need to complete their studies."* – P9.

As Koca (2016) asserts, motivating students is a basic, integral part of teaching and by implication, student support. As such, William and William (2011) suggests that motivation could be achieved by engaging students in meaningful and interactive activities. Xerri et al. (2018) argue that motivation is the basis of support regarding students' engagement with tasks and can influence students to perform optimally in each task leading to academic success.

Communicating with student was conceptualized as providing student support and was documented as:

- *"It entails communicating with students in all aspects to give them support to understand their work, enabling them to succeed in their studies."* – P7.
- *"Since this is a distance learning institution, one has to relax communication measures."* – P3
- *"Communicating early and on time with students is part of student support. It means that you engage them with problem areas with the aim of helping them to identify gaps and to ensure that they do not repeat them".* –P2.

- *“When I realise that they did not understand what was expected of them pertaining to assignments, I call them or send [an e-mail] and I offer them a second chance to rewrite.” – P1*

Communicating as revealed above could be interpreted as showing care by academics. As such, researchers such as Zawacki-Richter and Anderson (2014) highlight the importance of communication as support for students in distance learning. While Kim and Lundberg (2016) emphasise that it could strengthen students’ engagement and personal connection.

Theme 2: Strategies used by academics to facilitate student support.

It emerged that academics use various ICT systems and tutorial letters to provide support. Examples include video conferences and audio record clips; e-mails; sending SMS messages; telephone calls. Also, they use MyUnisa, discussion forums, audio record clips; video podcasts; videos and join-in hyperlinks; the Yammer platform; and tutorial letters.

The selected extracts on ICT use include:

- *“I conduct two video conference presentations per semester.” – P2.*
- *“I support students through video conferencing; hyperlinks; Yammer platform; discussions forums; discussions; audio record clips; video podcasts; videos and join-ins.” – P5.*
- *“In the past few years, I used video conference but now, TEAMS seem to be a more effective way to support students.” – P10.*
- *“I use short tippy tube presentations as my way of supporting students. Although the recordings are short, I believe they reach more students.” – P5*

Regarding sending e-mails, participants mentioned that

- *“The best way for me is to send detailed e-mails or call students. I have seen this strategy working for me in supporting students.” – P8.*
- *“I follow up where necessary by reading their e-mails carefully.” – P4.*
- *“I use e-mails and the telephone to support students. I found them to be more effective as not every student has a smart phone. For urgent messages, I request the secretary of the department to send SMS messages to students.” – P1.*
- *“E-mails are effective for me. I write detailed but specific e-mails as a way of supporting students. I use this especially.” – P7*

Furthermore, they elaborated by citing MyUnisa:

- *“I support students by using MyUnisa effectively and productively on a regular basis.” – P3.*

- *“I found using MyUnisa to be an effective way of supporting students. I ensure that student learn quickly to understand the process of using myUnisa.” –P9.*
- *“I integrate discussions and post announcements on myUnisa. I remind students about assignment dates as well as make another module-related announcement.” – P10.*

Regarding the use of tutorial letters, the following views were expressed:

- *“I set TL101 and TL201 [tutorial letters] in order to enable students to improve their note-taking skills.” – P3.*
- *“Tutorial letters 101 and 201 are other instruments of conventional support that include all students, even those who are far from ICT amenities like internet or do not possess smart phones”; also “ ... user-friendly tutorial letters written in a clear [way and which are] easy to understand with practical examples that may assist the student in preparing for the exams with ease...” – P9.*
- *Using tutorial letters is a very easy way to support students. Students can always go back and read what is expected of them and when to submit assignments and who to contact if they cannot get hold of their lectures.” – P1.*

Regarding individual consultations the views were expressed as:

- *“... accepting ‘walk-in’ appointments even if the student did not set up an appointment”; – P10.*
- *“... arrange by making appointments for students on request. I record the support provided in a book (journal).”*
- *“I make one-on-one meetings via TEAMS if the student requests to talk to me.” – P3.*

Evidently, academics use multiple strategies to provide support. This is in line with the ODeL mode of offering tuition which is mainly online. Similar findings were reported by Subotzky & Prinsloo (2011) and Matheson et al (2012) who mentioned that ICT plays an important role in ODeL for teaching and learning, research, and community engagement, and provides extended opportunities for students. On the other hand, Baloyi (2012) asserts that student support depends on ICT being available to all students. Rice et al. (2020) highlights the potential oppressive nature of online support. Hence, Stone (2019) recommends humanistic online approaches that embrace the recognition of students' learning experiences.

Theme 3: Enabling factors in promoting student support.

The enabling factors to enhance student support included e-tutors and ICT platforms.

Selected extracts include:

- *“Some of the enabling factors to support students include e-tutors. I engage e-tutors and work with them closely, but this is restricted or confined to students who are able to access all the available created platforms and forums.” – P8.*
- *“E-tutors make student support even better. They reach students that have been grouped under their support. More interaction and engagement are important and e-tutors fulfil this supportive role.” – P1.*
- *“My module has e-tutors, so I communicate with them and I check their activities on MyUnisa. When I check, I can already see how they support students.” – P4.*

E-tutors are a necessity for student support. They are the link between the academics and students and supplement learning. As (Krasnova & Demeshko 2015) indicate, E-tutors choose electronic educational content, conformable to lesson objectives, and create their own multimedia products including audio-recordings and video lectures to support students. Similarly, Klimova and Poulouva (2011), and Mkhize (2014) concluded that e-tutors provide guidance, and facilitate and monitor the learning process, which help the students to understand the concepts being taught. Instructions and guidance given by the e-tutor are intended to help eliminate technical problems and overcome obstacles so that students achieve their learning objectives.

Regarding available ICT platforms as enabling student support, the participants said:

“One big factor is using different modes of communication such as e-mails, MyUnisa, podcast. These make it easy to teach and support students” – P4,

“Functioning ICT pathways are an advantage to support students.” – P5,

“... variety of strategies such as video conference, MyUnisa discussion forums, posting announcements enable me to support students.” – P2,

Evidently, academics viewed different ICT platforms as enabling factors to enhance student support as it simplified and intensified learning activities. Furthermore, the advantage of online educational resources is that it can be downloaded to mobile devices, can be sent and shared with group mates, and can be discussed on forums (Krasnova & Demeshko 2015).

Theme 4: Challenges in providing student support.

Challenges in providing student support included addressing diverse students' needs and inadequacies of using ICT platforms and needs were identified as challenges experienced by academics.

Examples extracted on dealing with students' diverse needs include:

Challenge in dealing with students' diverse needs was highlighted in the following manner:

“I find it hard in dealing with students’ misunderstanding of internal processes and low attendance of students during discussion classes on TEAMS.” – P1.

“The biggest challenge is that students do not understand that here at Unisa, different sections are responsible for different things. A student calls you as a primary lecturer for finance issues or exams issues– P4.

“Students request help after hours because they work and study at the same time. If you want to help, you find out the problem is not related to the module you are responsible for. It is something else” – P6.

“Students mainly request help/support for administrative matters. ” – P8.

“Students [have] to buy data and airtime. They complain of insufficient funds to do so” – P7.

“The students in the deep rural areas are mostly neglected. Supporting them is a challenge.” – P1.

As Ma'mor et al (2022) indicate, some academics displayed inadequate competencies necessary to teach in an ODL context specifically those with special educational needs. On the other hand, Moonasamy and Naidoo (2022) also highlight the need to acknowledge inequalities from various communities in South Africa and how such inequalities affect students from accessing online learning.

Examples extracted on Inadequacies of using ICT platforms include:

“... many students are not able to access all, if not most of the support offered to them as much as Unisa creates several e-platforms.” – P7

“some students lack knowledge of accessing the internet.” – P10.

“...support is restricted or confined by students who are able to access ALL the available created platforms and forums. [It is] sad to say that most students fall through the cracks. – P2

“Students struggle to upload their assignments in the system” – P3

“...you can see that a student is challenged when the student submits a hand written assignment despite instructions that assignments should be typed. I experience this most of the time with first year undergraduate students. – P9

The extracts above highlight the gap between enabling resources such as availability of ICT applications and the challenges in accessing ICT by students. This confirms Arko- Achemfuor's (2017) view that studying at an ODeL institution can be problematic for many students. Also, Okoro et al (2021) found that some students had

lacked knowledge in manipulating online platforms. On the other hand, Lumadi (2021) also confirms that not every student studying online has access to cheap and unlimited internet.

Theme 5: Best decisions made by academics to provide student support.

The best decisions made by academics to provide student support included using their own discretion and following internal processes. Their views were expressed as:

“Conducting workshops with external markers on how they should provide constructive feedback to students’ assessment so that student can have a better understanding on what they have done wrong and how they were supposed to approach the questions.” – P9.

“Building and maintaining excellent relationships with the markers which are essential to the success of the implementation of the module and compiling comprehensive memoranda.” – P10.

“Maintaining regular ‘social presence’ through the MyUnisa discussion forum and a reasonable turnaround time to student queries.” – P5.

“I insisted on students making appointments for one-on-one, face-to-face sessions where I assisted with [subject] content instead of using a phone.” – P6.

Requesting feedback from e-tutors helps me to get a grip of what students are encountering. This also add to the information I gather when moderating scripts. Based on this, I collaborate with secondary lecturers to plan further support for students. – P10.

The above shows autonomy used by academics is proving student support as they can make their own decisions. Reflected in the responses is the importance of feedback, forming positive relationships with students and continuous support as valuable strategies to enhance student support.

7. Discussions and conclusions

This study focused on academics’ experiences on student support in an ODeL university in South Africa. It was premised on the view that student support is essential for academic attainment and that academics are central in ensuring that students are supported. Thus, from the findings, it can be concluded that academics conceptualise student support to include different aspects which imply that they view students holistically and student support contributes to academic attainment. Strategies used by academics’ commitment and caring for students. However, the issue on collaboration with student services support and the academic development and support units was missing from the expressions of academics. Although academics used ICT and tutorial letters to provide support, it was evident from the findings that not all students were able to access or use the ICT applications. The author suggests that this created barriers to learning because all assignments and examinations are completed online. Also, the fact that few modules have e-tutors creates inequity amongst students. More so, as

revealed in this study students also experience language barriers which could be alleviated when they interact with e-tutors.

8. Recommendations

Based on these findings, the following recommendations are made Student support should be an integrated and approached in a multidisciplinary way. Continuous professional development should include training on emotional and psychological well-being of students. Alternative accommodations should be made, and accelerated programmes implemented for students who battle to ICT usage. Language and academic skills training should be provided for students who need support as well as access to educational opportunities.

9. Limitation of the study

The limitation of the study includes a sample size and one college within the university where the study was conducted. Although this is a case, the study provides understanding regarding the academic experiences on student support. Academics were the only participants of this study. Support services personnel might have contributed different views about student support. Furthermore, undergraduate students may have different views and expectations of counselling support.

10. Future research

Research on multidisciplinary student support in ODeL institutions of higher learning could be conducted. Such research could inform student satisfaction and could improve the timeous completion of qualifications and reduce student dropouts.

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